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Revealing a Critical Discourse Analysis of Conservatism with Regard to Aldous Huxley's Brave New World

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ABSTRACT

This paper is an attempt to investigate the ideology of conservatism in Leonard Huxley's Brave New World from critically. Huxley's novel was selected for having the theme of conservatism. The study applies Van Dijk's model (2006) to analyze how conservatives structure their speech, focusing on lexical, syntactic, and social categories. Thus, three levels of structures are investigated. The first level (microstructure) deals with lexical, syntactic, and rhetorical categories. The second level (macrostructure) deals with categories, like power, identity, and dominance in affecting conservatism. The third level (superstructure) deals with how conservatives' speech is schemed. In Huxley's novel, it is found that most conservatives follow a negative lexicalization when describing others. Furthermore, simple sentences, declaratives, active voice, and the present simple tense are the most used syntactic categories by conservatives. Within social categories, the power of control, individual identity, and the value and value conflict model are the most prominent macro categories in conservatives' speeches. Lastly, conservatism has a special scheme that can be found in most conservatives' speech, which consists of introducing the topic, persuading or rejecting it, and closing the topic.

KEYWORDS: Critical Discourse Analysis, Conservatism, Three-structure Levels.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conservatism is the most influential political philosophy and ideology of the post-Enlightenment era. It has a great role in social life for its great effect (Ayatollahi, 2022a). For its long history, it has been dealt with differently through time. In other words, it is an ideology that embraces traditional values and has made its way to the present from the past. It supports ideas taken from old markets and private ownership and rejects quick changes. What marks conservatism is its paradox. In other words, some scholars consider conservatism an ideology, while others consider it a strategy to resist unwanted changes (Ayatollahi, 2022b; Ziegler, 2021).

Van Dijk (2015) state that some of the common tents that Critical Discourse Analysis (henceforth CDA) deals with are social, cultural, and ideological issues. This reveals that CDA is totally the appropriate approach that may deal with conservatism since the latter can be considered as a social cultural ideology (Ozcinar & Güven, 2021; Yu et al., 2024). Accordingly, CDA is used as a tool to discover the hidden ideology of conservatism in the selected novel about social groups (Azeez, 2024; Rasheed et al., 2023). Being highlighted by philosophers and linguists, Van Dijk (2015) claims that conservatism is regarded as a form of political ideology. It can be dealt with under the umbrella of **political** discourse. In this type of discourse, political power, power abuse, or dominance are reproduced. Additionally, it deals with social and political inequality in social groups. Commenting on Van Dijk's claim, it could be criticized as weak and unworkable in some situations. More clearly, conservatism is a general term. It could be assigned to various types of discourses depending on the type of discourse that it is involved in. That is, it could be social, cultural, religious, political, etc. Thus, one cannot limit one's use to one kind of discourse.

According to what has been stated, the present study tries to seek answers to the following questions:

1. How can conservatism be structured critically?
2. What kind of lexical orientation does conservatism have?
3. What are the syntactic categories that conservatives follow?
4. What are the rhetorical devices that mostly affect conservatism?
5. Which macro-categories can influence conservatism?
6. How is conservatism schemed?

In relation to the above questions, the following aims are put:

1. Investigating how conservatism can be structured.
2. Clarifying the lexical orientation that conservatism has.
3. Shedding light on the syntactic categories that conservatives follow.
4. Examining the rhetorical devices that can affect

conservatism.

5. Stating which macro-categories can influence conservatism.
6. Showing out how conservatism can be schemed.

Based on the mentioned aims, the study hypothesizes the following:

1. Conservatism can be structured according to several levels.
2. Conservatism has a certain kind of lexical orientation that can be positive or negative.
3. Some syntactic categories like sentence types, modes of sentences, voice, and tense are the most prominent categories that conservatives follow.
4. Rhetorically, rhetorical questions and repetitions are the most devices followed by conservatives.
5. Some macro-categories like power, identity, and dominance can influence conservatism.
6. Introducing the plot, accepting or rejecting, and closing the plot are the followed scheme by conservatives.

Lastly, the study is hoped to be valuable for those who have interests in linguistic, sociolinguistic, and critical domains. It is also supposed to be of value to those who have interests in literature or those who feel oppressed by social traditions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. *Conservatism: Definitions*

In his introduction to the 'philosophy of imperfection', O'Sullivan (2019) defines conservatism as:

An ideology that is characterized in the first instance, by opposition to the idea of total or radical change, and not by the absurd idea of opposition to change as such, or by any commitment to preserving all existing institutions. In late 1990s., Beiser (1992) tried to define conservatism as "a social attitude with a self-conscious conservatism that could be developed to be a social force". By self-conscious, Beiser means not merely implicit in behaviour, but consciously avowed, and ascribed to others. His definition can be regarded as the modern version of conservatism.

Recently, Eccleshall et al. (2014) see conservatism as a form of attitude in which conservatives "all favour a society in which certain inequalities are preserved, and in condemning purposive politics their intention is to ridicule the egalitarian ideals of their opponents". According to this definition, conservatism lacks morality, focusing on selfishness and this is the dark face of conservatism. To define conservatism as a form of resistance to change needs to be commented on. Here, the word 'change' has two meanings. It is either organic or artificial. The former refers to the fact that change starts automatically in society itself and, through time, has wide acceptance by people, i.e., bottom-up change. An example of this change is the role of women and their right to work in British society in the 20th C. The

latter refers to a top-down change in that a political party or an influential leader obliges people to follow a specific change. In terms of time, the first type, i.e., organic, is often lasted longer than the second type, i.e., artificial. Thus, the organic change can be described as 'demand driven' and the artificial as 'supply-driven' (Adorno et al., 1950; Gross & Glaser, 2021; Heryadi et al., 2023; O'hara, 2011; Xenopoulos et al., 2021). To sum up, conservatism can be defined as an ideology that has positive or negative attitudes towards social change. It is positive when a conservative intends to adapt to what is positive, neglecting aspects that do not fit modernity. It is negative when a conservative is totally blind to traditions. Further, it can be considered an approach to manage change and preserving tradition.

2.1.1. Views of Conservatism

To have deep insight into conservatism, one needs to understand its nature. Shedding light on its nature, it is found out that conservatism has four views (See figure 1). These views are:

i. Resistance to Change

Literally, the word conservatism implies three things: (a) supporting the existing institutions; (b) preference for traditional issues; and (c) the tendency to be reasonable and cautious. Counting these three factors together concludes that conservative societies will reject change unless it does not threaten their traditional directions

(Rotter, 1966).

ii. Conservatism as Playing Safe

Another aspect of conservatism is that there is a preference for "playing safe" and avoiding risks. In this viewpoint, an individual pretends to feel endangered and to experience insecurity in a complex and unacquainted environment and is therefore intolerant of change because it increases the complexity of the experiential world, i.e., the world is seen as falling apart (Rotter, 1966; Wilson, 2013).

iii. Conservatism as the "Generation Gap"

According to Harkin (2012), the total range of conservatism increases in those who belong to older generations than young people. In this sense, there will be a tendency to struggle between views of two generations which are later called the "Generation Gap".

iv. Conservatism as Internalization of "Parental" Prohibitions

Having a look on the final view of conservatism, conservatives see parental prohibitions or conventions as rules that are stable in each social phenomenon. Further, individuals' behaviors are evaluated according to these parental prohibitions. Clearly, the concept 'parental' does not only refer to those conventions or traditions taken from parents and grandfathers. Yet it also refers to the attitudes of peer groups, and other social institutions to which an individual is exposed to Sidanius and Pratto (2001).

Figure 1: Views of Conservatism.

2.2. Critical Discourse Analysis

To start with, Critical Discourse Analysis (henceforth CDA) is an analytical approach that aims at shedding light on social studies. It was initiated by critical linguistics, which emerged during the 1970s. CDA is not only an approach to discourse analysis. Rather, it is an approach that tries to present a different mode of analysis that includes other different fields like sociolinguistics, sociology, semiotics, stylistics, pragmatics, rhetoric, ethnography, etc. Discourse analysts argue that any science may interfere with the social structure of a given society (Van Dijk, 2015).

For Kress (1989), CDA is a theory that is different from all other theories in linguistics in that it could be described as an international theory. Thus, the following assumptions are made:

1. CDA analysts consider language as a social phenomenon.

2. Language of science and language of institutions are to some extent.
3. CDA analysts can express the values and meanings of individuals, institutions, and social groups through systematic ways.
4. There is no what is called "passive participants" in CDA. Thus, readers and hearers are treated differently.
5. In communication, texts are considered as the basic units.

The approach of CDA is to analyze the connection of text properties to social relations, which are not clear to users. In the same way, Thus, from the above highlighted views:

- a. CDA has a relation to social problems. It does not only focus on language and language use; rather, it focuses on linguistic characteristics in the social structure.

- b. Some social relations are performed and constructed through discourse, e.g., power.
- c. Society and culture are shaped and constituted by discourse in the same way that people shape discourse.
- d. Discourse is not neutral. In other words, in any discourse, one can find inequality, power, humiliation, etc. since each discourse may carry ideologies.
- e. Discourse cannot be understood without its context.
- f. For the interpretive and explanatory function that discourse analysis has, CDA aims at moving beyond these stages, i.e., interpretation and explanation, to interpret discourse in a very different way due to the social and cultural requirements.

According to these principles, CDA is a sort of social theory whose main goal is to show how some activities are socially committed. There are many approaches that discuss the notion of CDA. Among these approaches are those for the most prominent figures like Fairclough, Van Dijk, Each figure deals with CDA from a different point of view. In the current study, Van Dijk's approach is adapted in analyzing the selected data.

2.2.1. Van Dijk's (2006) Socio-Cognitive Approach

To start with, Van Dijk presents his socio-cognitive approach, which is portrayed as a form of social practice. Social practice here does not mean discursive practice. Rather, it focuses on social cognition, which connects text and society. In other words, Van Dijk (2015) states that the different forms of social cognition can be counted through CDA. By social cognitions he means "*socially shared representations of societal arrangements, groups and relations, as well as mental operations such as interpretation, thinking and arguing, inferencing and learning*".

Fundamentally, van Dijk's approach assumes that any social activity, involving discourse and text, has a mental dimension. That is, any level of discourse is treated as a mental model involved in the two levels of cognition: production and interpretation. Accordingly, ideology is considered social and cognitive (Van Dijk, 2015).

Besides, what makes van Dijk's approach special is its cognitive nature. Cognition is considered a turning point in CDA because most theories and approaches in CDA deal with text and its relation to speakers. In its general nature, cognition deals with mental processes and memory. In van Dijk's approach, there are three elements in cognitive structure: memory, mental model, and social cognition (Van Dijk, 2015).

Moreover, Van Dijk (2015) believes that to analyze a discourse, two levels are important to be involved in. They are the micro-level of analysis and the macro-level of analysis. By micro-level, he refers to the text structure, which focuses on grammatical and rhetorical elements in addition to coherence. On the other hand, macro-level analysis refers to broader notions like ideology, power, dominance, etc. Whatever is involved at the micro-level is put under the umbrella of the semantic model. Whereas macro-level strategies are put within the pragmatic model.

To conclude, van Dijk presents a three-fold approach. It consists of three main levels. They are cognition, society, and discourse. To analyze a text, critical discourse analysts do not only need theories of discourse structure. Rather, there is a need for mental representations to uncover the underlying knowledge, experiences, and ideologies. These underlying knowledge, experiences, and ideologies are better put in a social and cultural context. Such a relationship can be clearly shown in the following triangle.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1. Research Design

In the current study, the qualitative method is followed when it focuses on analyzing some extracts linguistically in relation to some social factors. Put differently, it focuses on words, situations, or contexts rather than numbers. Also, it follows a quantitative method when it deals with descriptive results, i.e., the statistical part in which frequency of occurrences and percentages are provided. Accordingly, one can say that the following method is the mixed method since both are used.

3.2. Data Collection

The data of this study are collected from Diken (2011), *Brave New World*. Five extracts are chosen to be analyzed according to Van Dijk (2015). The selected extracts are chosen deliberately for having the theme of conservatism.

3.3. The Model of the Analysis

In general, Van Dijk (2015) is adopted. The selected data are analyzed according to three levels: micro-level, macro-level, and super-structure level (See figure 2). At the micro-level, three categories are investigated, like lexical, syntactic, and rhetorical categories. In its macro-level, power (Van Dijk, 2015), identity (Sidanius & Pratto, 2001) are examined. In its third level, views of conservatism and the scheme are investigated (See Figure 3).

Figure 2: The Three-structure Levels of Conservatism.

a. Micro-structure Level

(1). Lexical Categories

Lexically, positive and negative categories are investigated. In other words, positive lexicalization denotes those words that have a positive orientation in describing others. While negative lexicalization refers to those words that have a negative orientation in describing others (Van Dijk, 2015). Accordingly, the present study highlights the most used type of lexicalization by conservatives (Hübener, 2023; Linjun & Yingxin, 2024; Zeb et al., 2024).

(2). Syntactic Categories

Syntactically, sentence types, moods of sentences, voice, and tenses are tested. In more detail, sentence types are investigated, whether the sentence is simple, compound, or complex. As for moods of sentences, declarative, imperative, and interrogative moods are shed light on. Also, it is important to examine the sentence's voice (active or passive). The last category is tense (Van Dijk, 2015). Investigating the tenses used by conservatives is an important concern since it may gain insight into whether conservatives live in the past or they keep up with the present (Gerace et al., 2022; Trnavac & Pöldvere, 2024).

(3). Rhetorical Categories

Within rhetorical categories, some rhetorical devices are investigated like metaphor, irony, repetition, and rhetorical questions (Al-Araji & Al-Azzawi, 2016).

b. Macro-structure Level

In this level, some categories that are clearly related to individuals like power, identity, and dominance are investigated.

(1). Power

Power is one of the most effective contextual factors that has a great impact on text. It is necessary to show who is the controller of the situation. In relation to the current study, power can take one of the three forms, i.e., as a control, as a threat, as a persuasive power (Pishwa & Schulze, 2014; Su & Yang, 2023; Xia et al., 2021).

(2). Identity

As it has been clarified in the earlier chapters, conservatives tend to defend some traditional ideas for the fact that they believe modernity can destroy their identity. Thus, identity is an important category in investigating. It can be individual or collective. It is individual if the conservative defends his/her personal ideas. It is collective if the conservative defends ideas of the whole society (Baggioni & Kasbarian, 1996).

(3). Dominance

In relation to dominance, inequality is treated clearly. In other words, whenever there is dominance, there is inequality. In turn, inequality is the core point in conservatism. Thus, dominance, in the current study, can be according to "Value and Value Conflict Model" or according to "Psychological Uncertainty and Anxiety Model" (Sidanius & Pratto, 2001).

c. Super-structure Level

In this level, two categories are investigated: views of conservatism and the scheme of conservatism. In relation to views of conservatism, resistance to change, playing safe, generation gap, and parental prohibition are the investigated views. As for the scheme, it shows how conservatives structure their speech.

Figure 3: The Developed Model of Study.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Extract (1)

Lenina was crying. "It's horrible, it's horrible," she kept repeating. "And how can you talk like that about not wanting to be a part of the social body? After all, everyone works for everyone else. We can't do without anyone. Even Epsilons."

"Yes, I know," said Bernard derisively. "Even Epsilons are useful"! So am I. And I damned well wish I weren't!"

Lenina was shocked by his blasphemy. "Bernard!" She protested in a voice of amazed distress. "How can you?" In a different key,

"How can I?" he repeated meditatively. "No, the real problem is: How is it that I can't, or rather-because, after all, I know quite well why I can't-what would it be like if I could, if I were free-not enslaved by my conditioning."

"But, Bernard, you're saying the most awful things."

"Don't you wish you were free, Lenina?" (Huxley, 1932: 83)

1. The Micro-structure Level

Lexically, the conservative Bernard uses negative lexicalization towards himself as in expressions like “damned”, “I can’t”, and “enslaved”. Contextually, these expressions are used to criticize the current political system in the World State city (an imaginary city). Thus, lexicalization can be considered as a negative lexicalization towards others. Syntactically, Bernard nearly uses all sentence types. In more detail, he uses the simple sentence once, and the compound and complex sentences twice for each. This indicates how confused he is in describing his ideas and beliefs. In relation to moods of sentence, it is found that Bernard focuses on using declarative modes to express his hesitated personality, e.g. “*How can I?*”, “*How is it that I can’t?*”, and “*Don’t you wish you were free, Lenina?*”. As for voice, Bernard keeps on using the active voice when talking to Lenina. This may indicate that he wants to make his voice heard by others that he refuses what other do. Besides, Bernard uses past and present simple tenses when talking to Lenina. He uses the present simple when he wants to describe his inability and he uses the past simple when he describes his wishes. This shows how powerless he is in this situation.

Rhetorically, Bernard uses metaphors in “*Yes, I know. Even Epsilons are useful, so am I*”. He compares himself to Epsilons who have freedom in choosing their destiny. He thinks that staying in this world means that he will be deprived of his freedom and self-decision. Furthermore, he keeps repeating the expression “*How can I?*”, “*I can’t*”, “*why I can’t*”, and “*if I could*”. All these expressions prove one fact that Bernard feels his incapability of doing anything. Also, he uses rhetorical question more than once along his speech as in “*How can I?*” and “*Don’t you wish you were free, Lenina?*”.

2. Macro-structure Level

Shedding light on macro-level power is used indirectly. In other words, along the text, it seems that both Lenina and Bernard try to convince each other with their own beliefs. Thus, one can say that Bernard follows a persuasive power on Lenina. Having a look at identity, it is found that Bernard (conservative) has an individual identity unlike Lenina who has a collective identity. Testing dominance, it seems that the inequality between Bernard and Lenina has its source in the psychological uncertainty model in the sense that Bernard does not know what he wants, he knows one thing that he cannot stay in the World State city.

3. Super-structure Level

Starting with views of conservatism, it seems that Bernard behaves as a conservative simply because he refuses the current change, i.e. resistance to change. As for the scheme, this extract starts with raising the topic by the anti-conservative (Lenina). Then, the conservative (Bernard) defends his point of view with presenting justification. Accordingly, the anti-conservative looks aimless. This makes the extract end with a rhetorical question raised by the conservative (Bernard).

Extract (2)

Bernard: “*Don’t you wish you were free, Lenina?*”

Lenina: “*I don’t know what you mean. I am free. Free to have the most wonderful time. Everybody’s happy nowadays.*”

He laughed, “*Yes, ‘Everybody’s happy nowadays.’ We begin giving the children that at five. But wouldn’t you like to be free to be happy in some other way, Lenina? In your own way, for example; not in everybody else’s way.*”

Lenina: “*I don’t know what you mean,*” she repeated. Then, turning to him, “*Oh, do let’s go back, Bernard,*” she besought; “*I do so hate it here.*” (Huxley, 1932: 83)

1. Micro-structure Level

To start with, Bernard uses negative lexicalization towards others through lexical words like “children”, “that”, and “five”. In other words, he blames the system on destroying children by giving them a sort of injection at the age of five. Such an injection decides what those children can be in the future whether slaves, employees with low jobs, etc. Shedding light on syntax, it is shown that Bernard uses the simple sentence once while he uses the compound sentence twice. There are no complex sentences. This shows the stability of Bernard’s personality. In other words, he arranges his ideas clearly so that he can present them steadily. As for sentence moods, Bernard uses declarative and interrogative modes when talking to Lenina. Interrogatives used by Bernard are not meant to be answered. Rather, he uses them to draw Lenina’s attention to something that she does not want to realize. Regarding voice, Bernard uses the active voice since he is confident having no fear in showing his personality. The last syntactic category is tense. It is obvious that Bernard uses the present simple tense when explaining his ideas and beliefs. In this extract, there is no indication that he, as a conservative, longs to the past.

Rhetorically, Bernard uses irony as in “*Yes, ‘Everybody’s happy nowadays.’*” Surely, he means the opposite since what decides people’s fate is the followed policy of the World State city. Likewise, Lenina’s repetition in expressions like “*I don’t know what you mean*” refers to the fact that she has no answer to what Bernard asks her for. About rhetorical questions, Bernard uses it twice in this extract as in “*Don’t you wish you were free, Lenina?*” and “*But wouldn’t you like to be free to be happy in some other way, Lenina?*”. Here, Bernard does not wait for an answer from Lenina. Rather, he tries to persuade her with his own beliefs.

2. Macro-structure Level

Investigating the macro-level, it seems that Bernard has the power that controls the text. This is due to the persuasive attitude that he follows when speaking to Lenina. Thus, one can say that persuasive power is used. As for identity, it is found that Bernard uses the collective identity through using the first plural personal pronoun “we” as in “*We begin giving the children that at five*”. By this, Bernard accuses himself of society of destroying the new generation, i.e. newborn babies. The last macro-category is dominance. It is obvious that value and value conflict is what is followed

by Bernard. Bernard finds that what happens in the World State city goes against his social values.

3. Super-structure Level

Shedding light on views of conservatism, resistance to change is what followed by Bernard. In other words, Bernard rejects what Lenina believes in simply because he refuses the new change that takes place in the World State city.

Schematically, the conservative (Bernard) introduces the topic. As for, the anti-conservative presents her view regarding freedom. Then, the conservative (Bernard) tries to persuade her with justification. Yet, she ends the topic with rejection.

Extract (3)

Lenina was quite offended. "Of course I can stand it. I only said it was lovely here because, well, because progress is lovely, isn't it?"

- "Five hundred repetitions once a week from thirteen to seventeen," said Bernard wearily, as though to himself. "What did you say?"

"I said that progress was lovely. That's why you mustn't come to the Reservation unless you really want to."

"But I do want to." "Very well, then," said Bernard; and it was almost a threat. (Huxley, 1932: 83)

1. Micro-structure Level

Having a look at lexical categories, Bernard uses negative lexicalization when describing others with lexical words like "threat". In other words, Bernard describes the current progress as a threat since it can threaten the future of the next generations. About syntactic categories, it is found that Bernard uses the simple sentence twice and the compound sentence once. There is no use for complex sentences. This shows how Bernard can arrange his ideas clearly to communicate with others, i.e., Lenina. As for moods of sentences, Bernard's sentences are put in the declarative mode which indicates that he is sure of what he is talking about. Furthermore, Bernard keeps using the active voice when talking to Lenina. Finally, he uses both past and present simple tenses. The past simple is used to describe an event that took place previously that Bernard cannot change it. Rhetorically, metaphor is not used in this extract. Rather, Bernard uses irony in his reply to Lenina "Very well, then". He is totally against Lenina's point of view regarding progress. In relation to repetition, it is found that the anti-conservative Lenina uses repetition with her phrase "progress was lovely". This indicates that the anti-conservative (Lenina) is the weakest in this challenge since she tries to prove her idea right unlike Bernard who looks confident. In addition, there is no use to rhetorical question.

2. Macro-structure Level

Here, some macro-social factors are investigated. They are macro because they work on larger levels than individuals. Accordingly, Bernard appears to have power (power of control) over Lenina in the sense that he has

self-confidence when talking to Lenina who seems to be hesitant. Furthermore, Bernard represents his individual identity for the fact that only he with his friend Watson are against the current progress at the time of accepting is with pleasure by most population. As for dominance, it is found "value and value conflict" is followed by Bernard in the sense that he feels that there is something, i.e. the current progress, that can threatens his value. As such, he appears to be conservative.

3. Super-structure Level

Having views of conservatism, it seems that the "generation gap" is what makes Bernard refuses the new progress. In other words, feeling that he belongs to a different era of time makes Bernard refuse the new behavior though he is at the same age as Lenina. In scheme, the topic is introduced by the anti-conservative (Lenina). Then, the conservative comments on it. Trying to persuade, Lenina presents some justifications. The conservative is hardly to conceive. Accordingly, he ends the topic criticizing it.

Extract (4)

"What a wonderfully intimate relationship," he said, deliberately outrageous. "And what an intensity of feeling it must generate! I often think one may have missed something in not having had a mother. And perhaps you've missed something in not being a mother, Lenina. Imagine yourself sitting there with a little baby of your own."

"Bernard! How can you?" The passage of an old woman with ophthalmia and a disease of the skin distracted her from her indignation.

"Let's go away," she begged. "I don't like it." (Huxley, 1932: 83)

1. Micro-structure Level

In the lexical level, it seems that Bernard accuses the policy in the World State city for depriving women from being mothers by breeding children through automatic machines. Accordingly, this can be considered as a negative lexicalization towards others by using certain lexical items like "not being a mother". In its syntactic level, it is found that Bernard uses compound sentences unlike Lenina who uses simple sentences. This is because Bernard has much to say to persuade Lenina with his ideas. On the contrary, Lenina has nothing to say. As such, she replies with two simple sentences. Moreover, Bernard uses the mood of exclamatory sentences twice to arise Lenina's interest with the idea of motherhood, but he uses the declarative mode once in order to explain his idea. In relation to voice, both Bernard and Lenina use active voice. This is because both have no fear in cancelling their own identities while talking about their ideas. Lastly, Bernard uses present simple and present perfect tenses while explaining his ideas and beliefs.

In the rhetorical level, the word "generate" is used metaphorically. In other words, the verb "generate" is often used to have technical meanings like "generate electricity". Thus, Bernard uses it to compare mothers and generator machines in that both can generate power. Further, there

is no use for irony in this extract. Rather, Bernard uses repetition through repeating expressions like “*something in not having had a mother*”. This is because of emphasis. In other words, he wants to emphasize that being a mother is something important. Finally, there is no mention for rhetorical question.

2. Macro-structure Level

To start with, it seems that Bernard has power in this extract over Lenina through using persuasive power. That is, he tries to persuade her by having an emotional issue like motherhood. As for identity, it is found that Bernard uses collective identity since missing motherhood is a shared issue. It cannot be an individual one. In relation to dominance, it is obvious that value and value conflict model is what is used by Bernard. He refuses the current policy of having children since it is against human instinct.

3. Super-structure Level

Regarding views of conservatism, “playing safe” is the view that is followed by Bernard. More clearly, Bernard feels that having a mother is safer to people than breeding children through electronic machines. As for the scheme, it is found that the Conservative (Bernard) introduces the topic. Nervously, the anti-conservative (Lenina) tries to evade the subject through ending it with rejection.

Extract (5)

“So hard for me to realize,” Bernard was saying, “to reconstruct. As though we were living on different planets, in different centuries. A mother, and all this dirt, and gods, and old age, and disease.”

He shook his head. “It’s almost inconceivable. I shall never understand, unless you explain.”

“Explain what?” John replied.

“This.” He indicated the pueblo.

“That.” And it was the little house outside the village.

“Everything. All your life.” Bernard said.

“But what is there to say?”

“From the beginning. As far back as you can remember.”

“As far back as I can remember.” John frowned. There was a long silence. (Huxley, 1932: 83)

1. Micro-structure Level

Lexically, Bernard uses negative lexicalization when describing others with words like “hard”, and “inconceivable”. In other words, after sending to Reservation in New Mexico, Bernard saw new people that have totally different conventions and habits that stand against his social norms. Thus, he seems offended. Syntactically, nearly, most of the sentences used by Bernard are complex. This may be due to his astonishment that makes him lose the ability to arrange his ideas clearly. About sentence moods, it is obvious that Bernard uses declaratives to explain what he feels at that moment. Furthermore, he uses active voice as an attempt to highlight his role in refusing the new social norms in New Mexico. As for tenses, Bernard uses three tenses. He uses present simple to describe his feelings, while he uses the past continuous to denote a hypothetical

assumption. The future is used to show Bernard’s state if he does not get enough explanation.

Rhetorically, a mother, dirt, gods, and disease are used metaphorically by Bernard. In other words, he wants to compare between the New Mexican society with the society in the World State city. Moreover, he mentions the words “mother” and “gods” with such negative words like “dirt” and “disease” to state people’s view for those identities (mother and god). Irony is not used in this extract. Emphasizing his astonishment, Bernard keeps repeating expressions like “hard to realize” and “never understand”. There is no use for rhetorical questions by Bernard in this extract since he is in need for an answer. As thus, rhetorical questions cannot be workable in this context.

2. Macro-structure Level

Starting with power, it looks that Bernard has power over John. The used power is power of control since he controls the situation during speaking. About identity, Bernard uses an individual identity since everything said represents Bernard’s point of view. In other words, Bernard is the only one who gets surprised with the new change though Lenina accompanied him. Thus, it is an individual identity. The last macro category is dominance. It seems that Bernard employs the psychological uncertainty model in this extract. This is clear through Bernard’s state with continuous asking for more explanations.

3. Super-structure Level

About views of conservatism, it seems that because of the gap generation, Bernard cannot accept the new change that existed in New Mexico. It is gap generation since those people who live in the World State city are totally different from those live in New Mexico. Schematically, the conservative (Bernard) introduces the topic with a sense of astonishment. Then, the anti-conservative (John) replies to him with wonder. Asking and replying, the topic ends with dissatisfaction by Bernard.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

To test the validity of the hypotheses, this section is considered. The arrived results are shown through the following descriptive statistical tables.

Table 1: Statistics of Lexicalization used by Conservatives.

No.	Types of Lexicalization	Fr.	%
1	Positive	0	0
2	Negative	5	100
3	Total	5	100

Commenting on Table 1, it is found out that all of conservatives uses negative lexicalization towards others when talking about their ideas and beliefs. Generally, this is normal since they keep on their beliefs simply because they things that what others follow is untruthful. This is shown clearly through the graphical representation below (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: The Graphical Representation of Conservatives' Lexicalization.

Table 2: Statistics of Syntactic Categories used by Conservatives.

No.	Syntactic Categories	Fr.	%	Total		
1	Sentence types	Simple	4	30.76	13	100%
		Compound	6	46.15		
		Complex	3	23.07		
2	Moods of sentences	Declarative	4	50	8	100%
		Imperative	0	0		
		Interrogative	2	25		
		Exclamatory	2	25		
3	Voice	Active	5	100	5	100%
		Passive	0	0		
4	Tense	Past	3	33.33	9	100%
		Present	5	55.55		
		Future	1	11.11		

Commenting on Table 2, it is found that conservatives mostly use compound sentences when expressing their ideas and beliefs in the sense that compound sentences have the highest percentage, i.e., 46.15%. Moreover, most of conservatives use the mood of declaratives, i.e., they have about 50%, since they have a light touch on listeners and easy to convey ideas. As for voice, nearly all conservatives use active voice when talking about their beliefs, i.e., it has the percentage of 100%. It seems that conservatives use active voice because they feel that their voices must be heard. Thus, their identities are not hidden while speaking. About tenses, it is shown that the present simple tense is the most used tense, i.e., it has about 55.55%, simply because

conservatives intend to change the present state comparing it to the past. This is proven through the percentage of using the past tense (33.33%). This is shown clearly through the following graphical representation (see Figure 5).

Table 3: Statistics of Rhetorical Categories Followed by Conservatism.

No.	Rhetorical categories	Fr.	%
1	Metaphor	3	23.07
2	Irony	2	15.38
3	Repetition	5	38.46
4	Rhetorical question	3	23.07
5	Total	13	99.98

Figure 5: The Graphical Representation of Syntactic Categories.

According to Table 3, it is shown that repetition is the most rhetorical device used by conservatives, i.e., it has about 38.46%. Such a percentage indicates that to emphasize their beliefs and ideologies, conservatives keep repeating what they are saying. About metaphor and rhetorical question, it is found that conservatives used them with the same percentage, i.e., 23.07% for both. This may indicate that conservatives intend to

use metaphor when they want to lessen the impact of their criticism, while they use rhetorical questions to express their exclamation. Besides, it is shown that conservatives use the rhetorical device "irony" rarely in the sense that it has about 15.38% percent. It is so since conservatives avoid using indirect when talking about their ideologies.

Table 4: Statistics of Macro-categories Followed by Conservatives.

No.	Macro-categories		Fr.	%	Total	
1	Power	Control	3	60	5	100
		Threat	0	0		
		Persuasion	2	40		
2	Identity	Individual	3	60	5	100
		Collective	2	40		
3	Dominance	Value and value conflict model	3	60	5	100
		Psychological model	2	40		

Regarding Table 4, it is obvious that power of control is the most followed power by conservatives in the sense that it has about 60%. Such a percentage may indicate that most conservatives control the situation when they talk about their ideas and belief for contextual factors. Furthermore, none of conservatives use the power of threat since threatening others cannot be affective with ideologies. Shedding light on identity, most conservatives use individual identity, i.e., it has about 60%, since their ideas and beliefs represent themselves rather than representing others. As for dominance, it is shown that the value conflict model is the mostly used model because most conservatives see that other's thoughts can threaten their own beliefs. Accordingly, others' beliefs conflict with conservatives' beliefs.

Table 5: Statistics of the Most Followed Views of Conservatism.

no.	Views of Conservatism	Fr.	%
1	Resistance to change	2	40
2	Playing safe	1	20
3	Gap generation	2	40
4	Parental prohibition	0	0
5	Total	5	100

According to Table 5, it seems that "resistance to change" and "gap generation" are the most presented views by conservatives in that each one has about 40%. Also, about 20% from conservatives present the view of "playing safe". It looks that conservatives employ the view of "playing safe" when they feel hesitated or fearing of something else. Because of the nature of the selected novel, the view of "parental prohibition" is not used.

Table 6: Statistics of the Scheme Followed by Conservatives.

No.	Schematic Items	Conservative		Anti-conservative		Total	
		Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%
1	Introducing the topic	3	60	2	40	5	100
2	Persuading other	2	66.66	1	33.33	3	100
3	Rejecting other	1	20	4	80	5	100
4	Ending the topic	2	40	3	60	5	100

Commenting on Table 6, it is found that most of conservatives introduce the topic of conservatism in the sense that it has about 60%. Moreover, those who try to persuade others with their ideas are conservatives. That is, their percentage is about 66.66% unlike anti-conservatives who do not care about the process of persuading others with their own beliefs. This supports conservatives in keeping and defending their ideology. As for affecting, it is shown that most of conservatives' attempts in affecting others ends with failure. This is clear through the item of rejection, i.e., about 80% of anti-conservatives reject conservatives' views. About the last item, it is found that most of situations are ended by anti-conservatives, i.e., it has about 6%. This is since most of anti-conservatives intend to end the talk in order to evade the situation or to

show that they are not interested in what conservatives talk about.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, some conclusions are reached for. These conclusions are basically associated with the hypotheses of the study. The conclusions of the study are:

1. According to Van Dijk (2015), conservatism is structured in three levels. They are micro-structure level, macro-structure level, and super-structure level. This verifies the first hypothesis (i.e., Conservatism can be structured according to several levels).
2. Negative lexicalization towards others is the lexical

- orientation that most conservatives follow. In other words, conservatives get used to use negative lexical items when describing others' ideologies. Accordingly, the second hypothesis is somehow proven (i.e., Conservatism has a certain kind of lexical orientation that can be positive or negative).
3. Syntactically, simple and compound sentences, declaratives, active voice, and the present simple are the most followed categories.
 4. In relation to rhetorical devices, metaphor, irony, repetition, and rhetorical questions are the followed devices by conservatives. Repetition is the mostly used device. This goes against the fourth hypothesis which states "rhetorical questions and metaphor are the most devices followed by conservatives".
 5. About macro-structure level, it is found that power (power of control), individual identity, and value conflict model (dominance) are the dominant categories that can influence conservatism. This validates the fifth hypothesis (i.e., some macro-categories like power, identity, and dominance can influence conservatism).
 6. Conservatism has the following scheme: introducing the topic, persuading or rejecting, and closing the topic. This verifies the sixth hypothesis (introducing the topic, accepting or rejecting, and closing the topic are the followed scheme by conservatives).

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